

Food sources of arsenic in pregnant Mediterranean women with high urine concentrations of this metalloid

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Abstract

Seafood consumption provides a significant amount of arsenic, although in its organic, non-toxic forms. Mediterranean populations may incorporate high levels of this metalloid as consequence of seafood consumption. In the present study, the significance of this input among pregnant women from a Mediterranean city (Sabadell, Catalonia, Spain) is assessed. Total urinary arsenic was analyzed in 489 pairs of urine samples, corresponding to the 12th and 32th weeks of pregnancy. Association of arsenic content with seafood and other dietary items were studied. Geometric mean concentrations were 34 and 37 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine during the first and third trimesters, respectively. The observed concentrations were similar to those reported in studies from other Mediterranean countries. The differences between both periods were not statistically significant. The only dietary factor significantly and positively associated with total urinary arsenic in both series of samples was seafood, particularly lean fish. Moreover, lean fish consumption during both periods was found to be the main determinant for differences in levels of arsenic between the first and third trimesters, which confirms the association between high levels of total urinary arsenic and seafood consumption.

1. Introduction

Arsenic is a metalloid widely present in the earth crust, occurring in trace quantities in rocks, soils, air and water. It can be found in inorganic forms such as arsenite (As(III)) and arsenate (As(V)) and their methylated species (monomethylarsenic and dimethylarsenic acids – MMA and DMA-, respectively) and is also a constituent of organic compounds such as arsenobetaine, arsenocholine, dimethylarsinylethanol, trimethylarsoniumlactate, arsenic-containing sugars or phospholipids, which are widely present in marine animals (Edmonds & Francesconi 1993). In addition to the natural sources, some anthropogenic activities can increase arsenic levels in the environment, such as mining, smelting of non-ferrous metals or burning of fossil fuels. Arsenic was also present in some pesticides used in the past (Abernathy et al. 2001).

Humans are exposed to arsenic by consumption of food and water (Abernathy et al. 2001). In some areas drinking water is an important source of exposure to inorganic arsenic (Vahter et al., 2006a). Nevertheless, food is generally the main contributor to the total arsenic daily intake. Rice may be one of the most important dietary sources. This cereal has higher efficiency for the assimilation of this metalloid from soils than other crops (Williams et al., 2007). Accordingly, areas with high arsenic in the water incorporate this metalloid by consumption of this cereal, e.g. Bangladesh (Vahter et al. 2006b). On the other hand, seafood is one of the most important sources of organic arsenic. In some populations the dietary load of this metalloid depends on the amount and kind of seafood consumption (Meltzer et al. 1994).

Exposure to arsenic has been found to be associated with diverse health effects such as skin lesions (Argos et al., 2011) and immunotoxicological (Ahmed et al., 2011; Andrew et al., 2011), cardiovascular (Chen et al., 2011; Yuan et al., 2011) and endocrine disorders (Chen et al., 2007). Arsenic is carcinogenic (non-threshold, class I human carcinogen; ATSDR 2007). It has been associated to skin, lung, bladder and liver cancer (International Agency for Cancer Research, 2004) and can cross the placental barrier (Concha et al., 1998). Prenatal exposure to arsenic from drinking water has been associated with reduction of birth weight in highly exposed populations (Rahman et

al. 2009), as well as neurodevelopmental defects (Hamadani et al., 2011; Parajuli et al., 2013). Increased blood pressure and anemia during pregnancy has also been related to arsenic exposure (Hopenhayn et al. 2006, Kwok et al. 2007).

Biomethylation is the most important way for detoxification of inorganic arsenic, MMA and DMA are less harmful and rapidly eliminated by urine. During pregnancy and lactation there is increased methylation, which may be a way to protect the fetus from high exposure to toxic arsenic. Nevertheless, during the first stages of pregnancy, when these processes are not fully enhanced and fetal susceptibility to possible harm is higher, prenatal exposure may be more important and may induce changes that could become apparent much later in life (Vahter 2009).

Arsenic in seafood is mostly present in the form of non-toxic organic compounds but seafood, especially shellfish, also contains small amounts of inorganic arsenic (Borak & Hosgood 2007). The arsenobetaine levels increase in humans after seafood intake but this compound is rapidly excreted. Populations with high seafood consumption, such as those in the Mediterranean area, have high arsenic urinary levels. Accordingly, it is important to confirm this origin in studies of urinary arsenic in human population, especially when prenatal exposure is considered.

In the present study, total urinary arsenic was determined in two different stages of pregnancy, representing the first and third trimesters, from a cohort of Mediterranean mothers. The influence of diet, with special emphasis in seafood consumption, on the observed concentrations of arsenic in urine was evaluated. Differences in exposure or excretion that eventually could have effects on prenatal exposure or future children development were assessed by urinary arsenic during both trimesters.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Urine samples

Between 2004 and 2006, in the context of the INMA research network (Childhood and environment) (Guxens et al. 2012), 657 pregnant women were recruited in their 12th week of pregnancy on occasion of a medical visit in the Primary Care Center II of Sant Fèlix Hospital (Sabadell, Catalonia). Recruitment conditions involved residence in Sabadell, age higher than 16 years, single pregnancy, voluntary incorporation to the program and scheduled birth at the Hospitals of Sabadell or Terrassa (a nearby city). Women suffering from chronic diseases, with communication impairment or assisted-reproduction pregnancy were excluded. After obtaining the consent from the admitted women, questionnaires were administered by trained interviewers in the 12th and 32th weeks of pregnancy.

Mean age of the mothers at the time of their last menstrual period was 31 years, ranging between 18 and 42 years. Their mean BMI before pregnancy was 23.62 kg/m², ranging between 17.35 and 54.82 kg/m², with 17.3 and 7.4% of overweight and obese women, respectively. 54.3% of the mothers were primiparous, 37.4% had another child and 8.2% had more than two children.

80 mL urine samples were drawn in both the 12th and 32nd week of pregnancy from 500 pregnant women of this cohort. The samples were stored at -20°C in polyethylene tubes until further processing. This study was approved by the Research Ethics Committee of the CREAL and all participant information was coded to maintain confidentiality.

2.2. Analysis of urine samples

498 urine samples from the 12th and 32nd week of pregnancy from the Sabadell cohort were analyzed for arsenic by quadrupole-inductively-coupled-plasma-mass-spectrometer (Q-ICP-MS). Prior to instrumental analysis, digestion and dilution of the samples was performed to oxidize and remove organic matter and to keep the concentrations of inorganic solids to a minimum (Castillo et al. 2008, Krachler et al. 2009). The digestion protocol was validated by processing a Bio-Rad Level 1 urine reference sample (Lyphochek Urine Metals Control 1-69131; Marnes-la-Coquette, France) that contains metal concentrations close to those of urine in the studied population.

3 mL of each urine sample were introduced in Teflon vessels, together with 3 mL of Instra-Analysed 65% HNO₃ (J.T. Baker, Germany) and 1.5 mL of Instra-Analysed 30% H₂O₂ (Baker). They were then left in an oven at 90°C overnight. After cooling, vessels were opened and placed on a heating plate at 250°C to evaporate the nitric acid. Once evaporated, the resulting solid samples were dissolved with 3 mL of 4% HNO₃ dilution, placed in 7 mL glass bottles and subsequently stored in a refrigerator until instrumental analysis. Before analysis, an internal standard of 10 ng/mL of In was introduced and depending on sample density samples were diluted with MilliQ water to 30 mL or 60 mL in order to avoid spectral interference. Analysis of the samples was performed with a Q-ICP-MS using a X-SERIES II device from Thermo Fisher SCIENTIFIC.

One MilliQ water blank was processed in each batch of samples for control of possible contamination. Instrumental limit of detection was 0.2 ng/mL. The method was validated by repeated analysis of Bio-Rad Level 1 reference urine samples (Lyphochek Urine Metals Control 1-69131; Marnes-la-Coquette, France) and the resulting inter-assay relative standard deviation coefficient was 4%.

All glassware and polypropilene material was thoroughly cleaned by soaking in 10% nitric acid for 24 h, followed by rinsing three times with MilliQ water. Teflon vessels were cleaned after every use by rinsing with 10% nitric acid (three times), then soaking with it in the oven at 90°C overnight, and finally rinsing with abundant MilliQ water.

Creatinine was determined at the Echevarne laboratory of Barcelona (Spain) by the Jaffé method (kinetic with target measurement, compensated method) with Beckman Coulter© reactive in AU5400 (IZASA®).

2.3. Statistical analysis

Descriptive statistical parameters were initially computed. Mean, standard deviation (SD), median, percentiles, minimum and maximum values were calculated as arsenic concentrations. Normality was tested by Kolmogorov-Smirnov test.

Arsenic concentrations during first and third trimester of pregnancy were compared using chi-squared tests and Spearman correlations. When the distributions were not Gaussian, Spearman correlation rates were calculated in order to define possible associations between different variables. Mann-Whitney and Kruskal-Wallis testing was therefore used to compare between groups of categorical variables. Univariate linear regression between log-transformed arsenic levels and different maternal variables was performed. Those variables showing $p < 0.20$ in univariate modeling were included in multivariate linear regression models.

Generalized additive models (GAM) were built in order to obtain graphics in which the associations could be clearly observed.

All statistical analyses were performed with Stata 12.0 software.

3. Results

3.1. Concentrations of total urinary arsenic during the first and third trimesters

Descriptive statistics are shown in Table 1. Arsenic was above the limit of detection in 99.8% of the urine samples. Geometric mean concentrations were 34 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine (55 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine of interquartile range) and 37 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine (55 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine of interquartile range) during the first and third trimesters, respectively. The concentrations were not statistically different between both periods and individual measurements between both trimesters were significantly correlated ($p < 0.001$). The distributions of concentrations were not normal because they were skewed to the right. P90 were 150 and 136 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine during the first and third trimesters, respectively.

3.2. Dietary factors influencing arsenic concentrations

No significant differences in seafood intake were found between the first and third trimesters (Table 2). Mean total seafood consumption during the first and third trimesters was 5.1 servings/week (69

g/day). 41% and 43% of this consumption corresponded to lean fish, 41% and 38% to fatty fish and 19% and 18% to shellfish, respectively.

According to the univariate models, the only dietary items having significant positive associations to arsenic levels in both trimesters were lean and fatty fish and total seafood consumption (first trimester linear beta coefficients 0.011, 0.0060, 0.0070; third trimester linear beta coefficients, 0.0084, 0.0055, 0.0046; $p < 0.001$, $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively; Table 3). Shellfish intake was significantly associated to arsenic concentrations in the urine of the first trimester (linear beta coefficient 0.013, $p < 0.05$). On the contrary, rice consumption showed significant negative associations with arsenic but only during the first trimester (linear beta coefficient -0.0039, $p < 0.05$). Other dietary items with significant negative associations were cakes/sweets during the first trimester (linear beta coefficient -0.0025, $p < 0.05$) and nuts during the third trimester (linear beta coefficient -0.021, $p < 0.01$). Eggs consumption showed a positive association with arsenic concentration in the urine collected in the first trimester (linear beta coefficient -0.014, $p < 0.05$).

3.3. Influence of seafood consumption

The trends found in the univariate models for lean fish and total seafood consumption were also observed upon quartile categorization of these variables (Table 4). Thus, lean fish consumption was significantly associated to arsenic concentrations in the urine collected in the first ($p < 0.001$) and third ($p < 0.01$) trimesters. Shellfish consumption was also associated to arsenic concentrations of urine collected in the first ($p < 0.01$) and third ($p < 0.05$) trimesters and fatty fish was associated to arsenic in the urine from the third trimester ($p < 0.05$). Total seafood consumption was associated to arsenic in urine from both trimesters ($p < 0.001$).

The quartile parametrization shows that the main differences were found when comparing the arsenic concentrations of the first quartile with the rest (Table 4). No significant differences were found between the third and fourth quartiles.

The results of a multivariate model considering diet, environmental exposure and maternal characteristics are shown in Table 5. Non dietary factors did not show significant associations in both trimesters. Lean fish consumption showed positive associations with arsenic in urine from the first ($p < 0.001$ and $p < 0.01$ in the third and fourth quartiles, respectively) and third trimesters ($p < 0.01$, $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.001$ in the second, third and fourth quartiles, respectively). No significant associations were found for fatty fish. Shellfish consumption showed positive associations with arsenic in the urine from the first ($p < 0.01$ in the second, third and fourth quartile) and third trimesters ($p < 0.05$ in the third quartile).

Elaboration of a multivariate model considering total seafood consumption instead of these seafood groups, resulted in significant associations between this diet component and arsenic concentrations in urine from both trimesters ($p < 0.001$). The significant positive association between total seafood consumption and urinary arsenic can be represented by GAM plots (Figure 1). These plots show that the main increase was found between 0 and 100 g/day of total consumption and that further increase did not result into higher urinary arsenic concentration.

Concerning other food items, the multivariate model also shows the significant negative associations between concentrations of arsenic and consumption of cakes/sweets ($p < 0.05$, first trimester) and nuts ($p < 0.001$, third trimester). Eggs showed a positive association with arsenic concentrations ($p < 0.05$, first trimester). All these significant associations were also observed in the univariate analysis. In contrast, the negative association of arsenic concentration and pasta/cereal in the univariate analysis was not retained in the multivariate model (Table 5). On the other hand, a positive association between arsenic concentration and consumption of vegetables was found ($p < 0.05$, third trimester). This association was not identified in the univariate analyses (Table 3).

4. Discussion

4.1. Arsenic concentrations

The arsenic urine concentrations in the mothers of the Sabadell cohort were lower than those found in populations exposed to waters contaminated with arsenic, such as Bangladesh (Gardner et al. 2010) or Antofagasta (Chile; Hopenhayn et al. 2003) (Table 6). The concentrations of the present study were also lower than in occupationally exposed individuals (Spain; Domingo et al. 2011). On the contrary, the levels for non-exposed population from European countries, Australia and USA were generally lower than those found in the present study (Brender et al. 2006, Caldwell et al. 2009, Callan et al. 2013, Link et al. 2007, Saoudi et al. 2012, Seifert et al. 2000). Nevertheless, studies from Mediterranean countries such as Italy, Croatia or Greece show arsenic concentrations in urine that are close to those in the present study (Miklavčič et al. 2012, Minoia et al. 1990), indicating that the Mediterranean populations have similar exposure to total arsenic in urine as in the Sabadell cohort.

4.2. Dietary arsenic sources

Rice consumption did not show any significant association with arsenic concentrations in urine. Consumption of this cereal has been associated with total arsenic levels in some studies concerning populations from sites with arsenic contaminated waters, e.g. Bangladesh (Vahter et al., 2006), but this is not the case in the Sabadell cohort. The associations between seafood consumption and arsenic concentrations observed in the present study are consistent with previous studies on general population. In a study of pregnant women from different Mediterranean countries, mean total seafood consumption was 40.4, 43.4 and 39.4 g/day in Italy, Croatia and Greece, respectively (Miklavčič et al. 2012). Considering that shellfish intake was not included in these estimations, the observed values are similar to the consumption reported by the mothers from Sabadell. The median concentrations of urinary arsenic in the women from these countries were 18, 24 and 37 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine for Italy, Croatia and Greece, respectively. The geometric means of the Sabadell cohort are 34-37 $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine (Table 1), in the high end of values observed in these Mediterranean countries, as it has been mentioned in the previous section. The significant differences in medians

from these three countries were attributed to fish consumption (Miklavčič et al., 2012). In agreement with these results, other studies on populations with lower fish consumption have reported lower arsenic content in the urine samples. Thus, in France more than 50% of participants reported fish consumption between once a week and twice a month (in our study only 11-13% of women would be included in this category) and found median levels of urinary arsenic that were 12 µg/g creatinine (Saoudi et al. 2012). In USA, the NHANES study indicated that 57.2% of population reported consuming fish between 1 and 4 times per month (Navas-Acien et al. 2011) and the concentrations of total urinary arsenic were 8.2 µg/g creatinine (Caldwell et al. 2009). The results of the Sabadell cohort and these previous studies provide a consistent relationship between fish consumption and arsenic intake that is general for western countries (Abernathy et al., 2001; Fontcuberta et al., 2011; Caldwell et al., 2009; Saoudi et al., 2012; Seifert et al., 2000; Brantsaeter et al., 2010; Meltzer et al., 2002).

In the Sabadell cohort, the highest association of urinary arsenic was found with ingestion of lean fish. This association is consistent with the results of one previous study considering the observed associations between food items, namely lean and fatty fish, and blood arsenic concentrations from Norwegian population (Brantsæter et al. 2012). Analyses of arsenic in different fish species have reported high concentrations in shark, monkfish, common dab, ray or sole and lower concentrations in fatty fish species such as anchovy, sardine, tuna, salmon or mackerel (Fontcuberta et al. 2011, Muñoz et al. 2000, Sirot et al. 2009). Studies of arsenic content in mollusks and some shellfish, such as crabs, shrimps, lobsters or octopus have also found high concentrations of this metalloid (Brooke & Evans 1981, Fontcuberta et al. 2011, Lunde 1973, Sirot et al. 2009). Shellfish has been reported to have higher influence than fish in urinary arsenic levels in one study from US population (Navas-Acien et al. 2011). On the contrary, in other cases the influence of shellfish in the concentrations of total arsenic, either in urine or blood, has been reported to be lower than fish (Brantsæter et al. 2012, Muñoz et al. 2000, Saoudi et al. 2012). Local

differences in shellfish, fish and their ecosystems, determining arsenic accumulation rates in the consumed species, may explain the differences between these studies.

Other dietary items, such as rice (Fontcuberta et al. 2011) and some vegetables, have been associated with arsenic ingestion but these cases are related with irrigation with water of high arsenic content (Vahter 2009), e.g. in Bangladesh the high content of arsenic in groundwater involved that local rice was an important source of this metalloid for the population (Gardner et al. 2010, Vahter et al. 2006a). In the Sabadell cohort seafood is the main source which far exceeds the other diet components as arsenic supplier.

It has been long demonstrated that arsenic coming from seafood is organic and non-toxic. In general, inorganic arsenic corresponds to less than 1% of total arsenic content (Fontcuberta et al. 2011). In some bivalves and crustaceans this proportion is higher but the organic forms are still predominant (Fontcuberta et al. 2011, Muñoz et al. 2000, Sirot et al. 2009). Most arsenic present in marine animal organisms is in the form of arsenobetaine which is inert and rapidly excreted (Borak & Hosgood 2007). Some studies have shown that subjects having ingested seafood in the past 24 hours had 10-fold higher levels of arsenobetaine in urine than those who had not (Navas-Acien et al. 2011; Caldwell et al., 2009). In some cases, an increase of inorganic arsenic is observed besides the organic compounds, (Miklavčič et al., 2012; Saoudi et al., 2012; Buchet et al., 1996) but the increase is small or negligible as found in some controlled experiments (Hsueh et al., 2002). Anyway the increase is considered biologically not significant due to its low level (Buchet et al. 1996). Accordingly, the high levels typically found in Mediterranean populations, such as the Sabadell cohort, should not be of concern for public health if it can be demonstrated that they originate from seafood ingestion.

4.3. Changes in urinary arsenic along pregnancy

The concentrations of total urinary arsenic during both trimesters were not significantly different. Along pregnancy, diverse changes and adaptations occur in the woman body, such as a 40-fold

increase in plasma volume (King 2000) and increases of the glomerular filtration rates (Swanson & King 1987). In the Sabadell cohort, these two metabolic modifications did not have any influence on arsenic urinary excretion. Increases of arsenic along pregnancy have been reported in studies on populations from sites contaminated with this metalloid which were attributed to increasing methylation as detoxification mechanism (Hopenhayn et al. 2003). In the present study, urinary arsenic was clearly related with seafood ingestion during the two periods of pregnancy.

As a matter of fact, grouping of the mothers by higher arsenic concentrations in the first or third trimesters shows a strong correspondence with seafood consumption (Table 7). Thus, the differences in mean consumption of white fish are statistically different among mothers with higher arsenic in the first than in the third trimester ($p < 0.01$) and vice versa ($p < 0.05$). These differences always involve highest intake in the group of highest arsenic concentration (Table 7). Significant differences are also observed among mean consumption of shellfish between mothers with higher arsenic in the third than in the first trimester ($p < 0.05$; Table 7) and total seafood in the mothers with highest arsenic in the first than in the third trimesters ($p < 0.01$; Table 7). Thus, in the Sabadell cohort the urine levels are closely associated to fish consumption which was the main contributor to the concentration differences between the first and third trimesters and the main predictor of arsenic levels in both periods.

An important limitation of the present study is the lack of arsenic speciation since it provides useful information on the origin and toxicity of this metalloid. When fish consumption is reported to be the main determinant of arsenic concentrations in urine it can be assumed that this metalloid is in its organic non-toxic forms but further chemical species assessment is recommended. In any case, the results of the present study prove that the urine concentrations from the Sabadell mothers are closely associated to diet. They do not reflect metabolic changes along pregnancy and this may be a feature of general population from sites not locally polluted with arsenic.

5. Conclusions

Mediterranean populations, such as the one represented by the Sabadell cohort, have higher total urinary arsenic concentrations than other European or North American populations. Consistently, the pregnant women from the Mediterranean region considered in this study have high arsenic levels. The high seafood consumption typical of these populations is the main cause for these high arsenic concentrations. A strong association between total urinary levels of arsenic and total seafood consumption is observed in the two different stages of pregnancy examined (first and third trimesters). Specifically, lean fish consumption is the main contributor to the intake of this metalloid. No significant differences in arsenic excretion are observed between these two periods and the observed small differences are mainly related to changes in lean fish consumption between the first and third trimesters. Seafood arsenic has been demonstrated to be mainly composed of organic species that are inert, not toxic and rapidly excreted. Therefore, these high levels of urinary arsenic found in Mediterranean populations are not cause of health concern. Assessment of the origin of arsenic in general population is important for evaluation of possible health effects in the exposed population. The approach described in the present study provides the necessary information for estimation of the possible toxic effects associated to arsenic accumulation.

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Table 1. Descriptive statistics of arsenic concentrations in urine from the first and third trimesters of pregnancy.

	% Detection	Arithmetic mean (SD)	Geometric mean (IQR)	P90	p-Value ^a	Spearman's correlation rho ^b
ng/mL						
1 st trimester	99.8	60 (141)	28 (44)	132	0.179	0.187 (p<0.001)
3 rd trimester	99.8	57 (83)	31 (51)	128		
µg/g creatinine						
1 st trimester	99.8	69 (121)	34 (55)	150	0.731	0.239 (p<0.001)
3 rd trimester	99.8	62 (79)	37 (55)	136		

^asignificance of the mean differences. ^bsignificance of the correlations.

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of fish consumption (g/day) during the first and third trimesters.

	Arithmetic mean (SD)	Median	Max	p-value ^a	Spearman's correlation rho ^b	% total seafood (mean)
Lean Fish						
1 st trimester	31 (22)	29	94	0.554	0.463 (p<0.001)	43
3 rd trimester	32 (23)	29	180			44
Fatty fish						
1 st trimester	26 (18)	21	100	0.453	0.453 (p<0.001)	38
3 rd trimester	26 (21)	21	182			38
Shellfish						
1 st trimester	12 (9.7)	10	70	0.030	0.427 (p<0.001)	19
3 rd trimester	11 (12)	10	185			18
Total seafood						
1 st trimester	69 (35)	65	198	0.302	0.526 (p<0.001)	-
3 rd trimester	69 (40)	64	399			-

Table 3. Univariate modeling of the arsenic concentrations in urine from pregnant women with different items from their diets. Beta coefficients (95% confidence interval) between log-transformed concentrations of arsenic in both trimesters and consumption of each dietary item (g/day) are shown (* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001).

	1st trimester	3r trimester
Dairy products	-0.00014 (-0.00059, 0.00031)	-0.00041 (-0.00079, 0.000031)
Eggs	0.014 (0.0013, 0.027)*	0.00011 (-0.0010, 0.010)
White meat	0.0024 (-0.0080, 0.0031)	-0.0041 (-0.0097, 0.0016)
Red meat	-0.0011 (-0.0047, 0.0024)	-0.0025 (-0.0059, 0.00094)
Lean fish	0.011 (0.0061, 0.015)***	0.0084 (0.0043, 0.013)***
Fatty fish	0.0060 (0.00048, 0.011)*	0.0055 (0.00097, 0.010)*
Shellfish	0.013 (0.0027)*	0.0027 (-0.0056, 0.011)
Total seafood	0.0070 (0.0041, 0.010)***	0.0046 (0.0022, 0.0069)***
Vegetables	0.000033 (-0.00092)	0.00064 (-0.00021, 0.0015)
Fruit	-0.00023 (-0.00071, 0.00026)	-0.00037 (-0.00079, 0.000044)
Nuts	-0.0092 (-0.023, 0.00044)	-0.021 (-0.034, -0.0074)**
Legumes	-0.0012 (-0.0057, 0.0033)	-0.0018 (-0.0053, 0.0017)
Pasta/Cereal	-0.0020 (-0.0057, -0.0017)*	-0.0016 (-0.0051, 0.0020)
Rice	-0.0039 (-0.0071, -0.00076)*	0.0021 (-0.0048, 0.00053)
Potatoes	0.00059 (-0.0021, 0.0033)	-0.0024 (-0.0053, 0.00052)
Bread	0.00084 (-0.0017, 0.0034)	-0.0018 (-0.0042, 0.00051)
Cakes/sweet things	-0.0030 (-0.0057, -0.00028)*	-0.0024 (-0.0047, 0.0000017)
Coffee/infusions	-0.00029 (-0.00085, 0.00027)	0.000031 (-0.00048, 0.00054)

*p<0.05; **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

Table 4. Mean (standard deviation) of the concentrations of urinary arsenic (in $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine) during the first and third trimesters of pregnancy grouped by quartiles of fish consumption (g/week).

Consumption quartile	White fish		Fatty fish		Shellfish		Total seafood	
	1 st trim	3 rd trim						
1 st	50 (72)	44 (45)	56 (69)	56 (78)	50 (94)	48 (55)	45 (62)	41 (46)
2 nd	56 (73)	63 (68)	86 (188)	65 (106)	78 (141)	65 (81)	52 (75)	61 (64)
3 rd	97 (168)	67 (92)	69 (110)	58 (57)	66 (75)	82 (108)	103 (195)	74 (112)
4 th	88 (159)	85 (111)	64 (76)	69 (73)	78 (145)	56 (68)	75 (92)	71 (77)
^a P	0.0001	0.001	0.45	0.022	0.001	0.040	0.0001	0.0004

^ap of significance according to Kruskal-Wallis test.

Table 5. Multivariate modeling of the urine arsenic concentrations in both trimesters of pregnancy and maternal characteristics and different variables of exposure. Beta coefficients (95% confidence interval) between log-transformed concentrations of arsenic in both trimesters and maternal characteristics are shown. Fish consumption was analyzed by separation of different types of fish. (* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001)

	1st trimester	3r trimester
Exposure to heavy truck traffic		
Practically never	1	1
Rarely	-0.0035 (-0.27, 0.26)	0.067 (-0.31, 0.17)
Regularly	-0.23 (-0.55, 0.10)	-0.29 (-0.58, -0.0057)
Heavily	-0.085 (-0.35, 0.18)	-0.086 (-0.33, 0.15)
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	-0.024 (-0.048, -0.00084)*	-0.033 (-0.054, -0.0.11)**
Maternal origin		
Spain	1	1
Latin America	-0.26 (-0.72, 0.20)	-0.036 (-0.45, 0.39)
Rest of Europe	-0.17 (-0.87, 0.52)	-1.1 (-1.7, -0.45)**
Rest of the world	0.68 (-0.91, 2.3)	-0.27 (-1.7, 1.1)
Social class (3 cat)		
I+II	1	1
III	0.072 (-0.22, 0.37)	-0.010 (-0.27, 0.25)
IV+V	0.19 (-0.087, 0.48)	-0.11 (-0.36, 0.14)
Parity		
No previous children	1	1
1 children	-0.18 (-0.41, 0.037)	-0.055 (-0.25, 0.14)
2 or more children	-0.24 (-0.63, 0.16)	-0.11 (-0.48, 0.25)
Age of the home (yr)	-0.015 (-0.095, 0.066)	-0.092 (-0.16, -0.020)*
Physical exercise		
Sedentary / low activity	1	1
Moderate	-0.16 (-0.42, 0.088)	-0.22 (-0.44, -0.011)*
Quite a lot / very active	-0.046 (-0.33, 0.24)	0.047 (-0.20, 0.29)
Dietary items (g/day)		
Dairy products	-0.000073 (-0.00053, 0.00038)	-0.00036 (-0.00075, -0.00002)
White meat	-0.0033 (-0.0091, 0.0026)	-0.0043 (-0.010, 0.0014)
Red meat	-0.00040 (-0.0040, 0.0031)	0.00067 (-0.0028, 0.0041)
Eggs	0.015 (0.0021, 0.028)*	0.00033 (-0.0096, 0.010)
White fish		
1 st quartile	1	1
2 nd quartile	0.13 (-0.18, 0.43)	0.34 (0.093, 0.59)**
3 rd quartile	0.62 (0.32, 0.93)***	0.31 (0.037, 0.57)*
4 th quartile	0.51 (0.22, 0.79)**	0.51 (0.24, 0.79)***
Fatty fish		
1 st quartile	1	1
2 nd quartile	-0.010 (-0.30, 0.28)	-0.12 (-0.39, 0.16)
3 rd quartile	0.074 (-0.24, 0.39)	-0.10 (-0.37, 0.17)
4 th quartile	0.0048 (-0.30, 0.31)	0.046 (-0.25, 0.34)
Shellfish		
1 st quartile	1	1
2 nd quartile	0.49 (0.20, 0.77)**	0.11 (-0.14, 0.35)
3 rd quartile	0.48 (0.15, 0.80)**	0.34 (0.056, 0.63)*
4 th quartile	0.45 (0.14, 0.76)**	0.12 (-0.16, 0.41)
Vegetables	-0.00024 (-0.0012, 0.00074)	0.0011 (0.00021, 0.0021)*

Fruit	-0.00031 (0.00083, 0.00021)	-0.00043 (-0.00086, 0.000033)
Potatoes	0.0011 (-0.0016, 0.0039)	-0.00035 (-0.0034, 0.0027)
Bread	0.00015 (-0.0040, 0.0027)	-0.00069 (-0.0030, 0.0016)
Pasta / cereal	-0.0016 (-0.0040, 0.00084)	-0.0011 (-0.0032, 0.0013)
Nuts	-0.0091 (-0.023, 0.0048)	-0.024 (-0.037, -0.010)**
Cakes/sweet things	-0.0029 (-0.0057, -0.00016)*	-0.0012 (-0.0037, 0.0012)
r^2	0.16	0.21

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$

Table 6. Comparison of the arsenic concentrations in urine of pregnant women from Sabadell with urine concentrations from other populations.

Reference	Sampling years	N	Location	As ^k
Present work ^a	2004-06	489	Sabadell – 1st trim	28
Present work ^a	2004-06	489	Sabadell – 3rd trim	31
Link et al. 2007 ^{ah}	2002-03	500	South Germany	4.6 ^d
Caldwell et al., 2009 ^{ag}	2003-04	2500	USA	8.2
Banza et al. 2009 ^{bg}	2006-07	179	DR Congo	18
Seifert et al., 2000 ^{bg}	1990-92	4000	Germany	4.6
Saoudi et al., 2012 ^{bi}	2006-07	1515	France	12
Hopenhayn et al., 2003 ^{ae}	1998-00	29	Chile	58
Garner et al., 2010 ^{be}	2001-03	500	Bangladesh	94
Brender et al., 2006 ^{ae}	1995-2000	74	Texas (Mexican origin)	9.0
Minoia et al., 1990 ^{bg}	Nr	540	Italy	17 ^d
Miklavcic et al., 2012 ^{ae}	2007-2009	900	Italy	18
Miklavcic et al., 2012 ^{ae}	2007-2008	234	Croatia	24
Miklavcic et al., 2012 ^{ae}	2006-2009	484	Greece	37
Domingo et al., 2001 ^{bf}	Nr ^j	28	Spain ^f	76
Callan et al., 2013 ^{ae}	2008-2001	173	Australia	13

^aMedian. ^bGeometric mean. ^cArithmetic mean. ^dµg/L ^ePregnant women.

^fOccupational exposure. ^gGeneral population (including children). ^hChildren. ⁱGeneral population (only adults). ^jnot reported. ^kµg/g creatinine.

Table 7. Mean (standard deviation) of the fish consumption (in g/day) during the first and third trimesters of pregnancy grouped for differentiation of women with higher arsenic concentrations in these periods.

Consumption period	White fish		Fatty fish		Shellfish		Total seafood	
	1 st > 3 rd	3 rd > 1 st	1 st > 3 rd	3 rd > 1 st	1 st > 3 rd	3 rd > 1 st	1 st > 3 rd	3 rd > 1 st
First	34 (22)	29 (22)	27 (21)	26 (18)	12 (9.2)	12 (10)	73 (36)	66 (34)
Third	31 (24)	32 (23)	25 (21)	28 (21)	12 (8.9)	11 (14)	68 (40)	70 (40)
P ^a	0.0039	0.0497	0.38	0.51	0.31	0.042	0.0072	0.26

^ap of significance according to Kruskal-Wallis test.

Figure captions

Figure 1. Graphic representation of a general additive model showing the relationship (and 95% confidence levels) of total arsenic levels in urine (Y axis: $\mu\text{g/g}$ creatinine; log-transformed) and total seafood consumption (g/day) taken as continuous variable (X-axis). The symbols (+) on the X-axis show total seafood consumption of each subject.